

Effect of Non Financial Disclosure on Performance of Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to analyse the effect of non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of intellectual capital disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria. Evaluate the effect of risk management disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria and investigate the effect of corporate governance disclosure on firm value. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design because the data for the study are secondary data that were sourced from financial publications such as the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) Fact Book and Daily Official List for the study. To analyze the data, the study used statistical tools involving the Descriptive Statistics, correlation analysis and the Ordinary Least Square Regressions (OLS). The regression result indicates that intellectual capital disclosure, risk management disclosure and corporate governance disclosure has positive and significant effects firm value in Nigeria. The study thus concludes that non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria. Amongst the recommendation is that management of quoted firms in Nigeria should formulate policy that will be geared toward enhancing intellectual capital disclosure. Increasing firm Risk management disclosure will significantly affect firm value in Nigeria. The study recommends that management of quoted firms in their drive to enhance firm value; management should increase and improve risk management disclosure and management of quoted firm should improve in corporate governance disclosure.

Keywords: Non Financial Disclosure, Consumer Goods Firms, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Information plays an important role in the corporate world as it can benefit companies in many ways (Precious, Eno & Joseph, (2025). The information provided in annual reports or corporate reporting includes financial and non-financial information (NFI). However, recent decades has witnessed the rise attention on NFI due to inadequacy of traditional financial information reporting to fulfill the need in assessing the organization value (PWC, 2022). Companies however have moved from passive to active information disclosure, from strict to know compliance disclosure to right to know complete disclosure and they are aspiring to link corporate strategy with one comprehensive stream of nonfinancial and financial data (Muyiwa, Gbenga, Joseph & Olayinka, 2024). The relevance and inclusion of non-financial information in corporate reporting contributes greatly to information transparency and is therefore an issue of great significance in economies throughout the world (Soomiyol, Adesoji & Yua, 2025). A growing number of organizations are publishing information evidencing the impact made by their

activities on the environment, corporate governance, society, and human rights. This increased visibility of non-financial information has heightened awareness of the importance of these reports in reflecting organizational status and practices. Over recent years, the level of interest from stakeholders in corporate environmental, social and ethical performance has risen significantly. Non-financial information however enables businesses to be transparent in communicating these non financial aspects of their management and performance. It also enables business to be accountable to internal and external stakeholders for organizational performance towards the goal of sustainable development owing to continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce, their families, the local community and society at large (Firmansyah, Umar, & Jibril (2023).

Shaikh (2022) argue that non financial information is as important as financial information in the decision-making process. Both pieces of information contain valuable insights that can yield interesting results if used correctly. The studies noted that investors disregard non financial information in their investment decision making and only fewer literature have addressed on its usefulness and relevance for investors' decision making.

In Nigeria, non financial disclosures are regulated by code of corporate governance 2018 which covers all the categories of non financial disclosures (environment, governance, human resources, risk management and society); National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007 & 2008; Environmental Impact Assessment Act 2004; Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provision) Act 2004; Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection Act 2007 etc which centered on review of regulations on air and water quality, discharge of effluents and other harmful substances as well as control of other forms of environmental pollution. These laws covered the environmental and societal aspect of non financial disclosures.

At international level, non financial disclosures have attracted considerable interest from a number of key stakeholders such as the United Nations Global Compact, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC), and the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB), the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) and European Commission Guidelines on Reporting

Nevertheless, Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) guidelines on reporting principles and standard disclosures are still the most authoritative in the international arena (KPMG, 2017; Laura, Maria, and Helena, 2018). Based on a survey of the theoretical and empirical literature on GRI, the guideline on content index in accordance with G3 or G3.1 or G4 is strenuous but provides most effective result (Haller 2017). The guidelines however covered all the categories of non financial disclosures ranging from environment, governance, human resources, risk management and society

The disclosure of non-financial information is a strategic action that fundamentally improves the communication of organizations with their stakeholders (Okolie & Igaga, 2021). Thus, a recent study by Ernst and Young (2017) highlighted the major significance of this information for users, and pointed out that 38% of investors acknowledged making use of such reports in reaching their investment decisions and over the past two decades, there have been many ideas to improve business reporting, and nearly all of them focus on the importance of companies providing more NFI. Against the aforementioned observation, this study is established to examine the effect of non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria (Bek-Gaik & Surowiec, 2021)

Statement of Problem

The issue of non financial information has been debated in the recent years, latest analyses by Nwakoby (2020) reported that most investors disregard non financial information (NFI) disclosures in investment decision making process as it could not meet their expectations. Consistent with this argument, Ernst and Young (2022) pointed out that only 38 percent of investors acknowledged making use of NFI in reaching investment decisions as emphasis were on financial information. Odili (2022) also noted that ratio analysis and other interpretation techniques on the financial statements cannot measure all aspects of performance. For example, the effect of a business on the environment cannot be measured using

financial criteria, but is increasingly regarded as an important aspect for investors' decision making. Despite the continued use of financial information in the decision making by private sectors in Nigeria, there has been a continued failure of private entities in Nigeria. The study however expressed concerns over the significant rise in the need for non-financial reporting (NFR) in the recent years and its relevance for investors' decision making is yet to be investigated.

Several stakeholders have also expressed concerns over the need for NFI to meet their expectations and not much have been done in academic literature in addressing the usefulness and relevance of non financial information disclosures for investors decision making.

In the developed nations, attempts were made as follows; Omaliko, Nwadiolor, and Nweze (2020) investigated intellectual capital disclosure (ICD) and firms' performance in Germany and France respectively using disclosure index by GRI G4 and found insignificant effect. Cloudy and Oday (2022) found insignificant negative effect on risk management disclosure (RMD) and firms performance. On the contrary, Oliveira, Rodrigues and Craig (2022) found significant positive effect. Wan and Sulong (2015) also reported that corporate governance disclosure (CGD) using disclosure index by GRI G4 did not correlate with financial performance of firms. In contrast, Rouf (2022) found that corporate governance disclosure (CGD) was positively related with firms' profitability.

The previous literatures researched in the developed nations as shown above discussed non financial disclosures (NFDs) measured using IC, RM and CG independently which couldn't meet the expectations of the investors (Abdulateif 2023; Wang 2022; Stefano and Clodia 2022; Abdulateif 2023) Owing to the investors' needs, those categories of non financial disclosures (IC, RM and CG) were combined to develop a model fit on Non financial disclosure raging from human resources, risk management to corporate governance as they is a gap in knowledge on the joint effect of these categories of Non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in developing nations.

In the developing nations, efforts were made in examining the usefulness and relevance of non financial information disclosures in meeting the expectations of the investors as follows;

Oday (2022) examined intellectual capital disclosure (ICD), risk management disclosures (RMD) and firms' profitability and reported significant positive effect. This disagrees with Odugbemi and Igbekoyi (2021) who found insignificant effect between intellectual capital disclosure (ICD) and firms' performance Igbekoyi et al. (2021) on the same note found significant positive effect between corporate governance disclosures and firms performance. Ismail and Dilling (2020) found significant positive relationship between risk management disclosures (RMD) and firms' performance. In agreement, Yusuf (2016); reported significant positive effect on risk management disclosure (RMD) and firms' performance As it can also be seen in the literature reviewed in the developing nations, the following lapses were noted; none of these studies adopted any guideline by international key stakeholders especially the GRI guideline on content index in accordance with G3or G3.1or G4 which stills the most authoritative in the international arena (KPMG, 2017; Laura, Maria, and Helena, 2018). Secondly, the studies covered only financial service sector, oil and gas sector, consumer goods sector and industrial goods sector. Thirdly, only the study of Raheman, Salleh, Afza and Chek (2022) attempted and covered two major categories of NFDs leaving the other categories unattended which calls for further investigation and no study had addressed on this in both developed and developing nations.

Based on these observations the present study will analyse the f effect of non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Non Financial Disclosures

In the recent decade, non financial information disclosure has witnessed and gained a growing attention and recognition in the developing and emerging nations due to inadequacy of traditional financial information reporting to fulfill the need in assessing the organization value (PWC, 2017). The study also pointed out that most top managers and executives in multinational companies believe that non-financial

performance measures outweigh financial performance measures in terms of creating and measuring long-term shareholder value.

According to Yusuf (2016), non-financial disclosures are those metrics which include index scores, ratios, counts and other information not presented in the basic financial statements. Corporate organizations have moved from passive to active information disclosure, from strict to know compliance disclosure to right to know complete disclosure and they are aspiring to link corporate strategy with one comprehensive stream of non financial and financial data (Maxwell, Smith and Brewster, 2010).

According to Robb, Single, and Zarzeski, (2011), NFI disclosure is viewed as qualitative information in the companies' reports which exclude financial statements and related footnotes. According to PWC (2017), non financial disclosures are used to reference all information outside the financial statements (metrics and narratives). It is recognized that NFDs may be an imperfect term as the information may ultimately have a financial dimension or impact.

The study of Okoye (2016) measured non financial disclosure using Intellectual Capital Disclosure (ICD). Risk Management Disclosure was used as a proxy for non financial disclosure by Ismail and Rahman, (2013), Rouf (2016) proxy non financial disclosure using Corporate Governance Disclosure

For the purpose of this research, the present study developed a model fit on non financial disclosures using the following Indexes; Intellectual Capital Disclosure (ICD), Risk Management Disclosure (RMD) and Corporate Governance Disclosure (CGD).

The relationship between non-financial disclosure and firm performance has become a focal point in contemporary corporate governance and sustainability discourse. Non-financial disclosure encompasses the voluntary communication of information by businesses that goes beyond traditional financial metrics, shedding light on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices (Huynh, 2020). As companies increasingly recognize the significance of their societal and environmental impact, stakeholders demand greater transparency and accountability (Jiang et al., 2022). Non-financial disclosure can take various forms, including sustainability reports, corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives, and disclosures related to ethical business practices (Stefano & Clodia, 2022). These disclosures aim to provide stakeholders with a holistic understanding of a company's commitment to sustainable and responsible business practices. The link between such disclosures and firm performance is multifaceted and manifests in several dimensions.

Robust non-financial disclosure can enhance a company's reputation and build trust among stakeholders. Stakeholders, including customers, investors, and employees, often prefer businesses with transparent and ethical practices, influencing their perception of the company and, consequently, its performance (Sougne & Lakhal, 2015). Non-financial disclosures often include information on a company's approach to risk management, especially in areas such as environmental impact, supply chain ethics, and social responsibility. Effective risk management, as communicated through non-financial disclosures, can contribute to the resilience of the business, and protect against potential financial setbacks. Companies that actively disclose non-financial information related to innovation, research and development, and sustainable practices may gain a competitive advantage. Such disclosures can attract socially conscious investors and consumers, fostering innovation and securing a unique market position (Stefano & Clodia, 2022).

Non-financial disclosures related to corporate culture, diversity and inclusion, and employee well-being can impact a company's ability to attract and retain talent. A positive workplace environment, as communicated through disclosures, can contribute to higher employee engagement and productivity. Non-financial disclosure often intersects with regulatory requirements and standards. Companies that proactively disclose information aligned with industry standards and regulations may mitigate legal risks and demonstrate a commitment to compliance, positively influencing firm performance. Investors increasingly consider non-financial factors when evaluating a company's long-term sustainability (Boluwaji, et al., 2024; Igbekoyi et al., 2021).

Intellectual Capital Disclosure

The Intellectual Capital disclosure reflects the corporate performance whereby it encourages users' better decision making and evaluation on the company for preceding periods as well as alleviating ambiguity as economic value derives from production of goods and creation of Intellectual Capital (Azman and Kamaluddin, 2009).

Intellectual Capital reporting has received significant attention among academics and research practitioners across the world (Abeysekera and Guthrie, 2014). It is recognized as a vital asset and value creator to companies in gaining a key source of competitive advantage compared to its competitors.

Stewart (2017) defines it as "Packaged useful knowledge". Sullivan (2010) saw it as knowledge that can be converted into profit. Roos and Roos (2017) state that intellectual capital is sum of knowledge of its members and practical translation of this knowledge into brands trademarks and processes. Edvinson and Malone (2017) define it as the possession of knowledge, applied experiences, organizational technology, customer's relations and professional skills that provide a company with a competitive edge in the market. According to Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance 2018, paying adequate attention to employees and occupational health and safety ensures successful long term business performance of the company.

The following is recommended by NCCG 2018 as regard to ICD;

1. report on the management of safety issues including workplace accidents, fatalities, occupational and safety incidents;
2. plans and strategy for addressing and managing the impact of serious diseases on the company's employees and their families;
3. training initiatives, employee development and the associated financial investment;
4. The position of Global Reporting Initiative (G4-LA2, LA5, LA6, LA7 and LA8) on adequate disclosure on intellectual capital is as follows:
5. report on the benefits which are standard for full-time employees of the organization and availability of skills needed to achieve goals
6. report on availability and applicability of information systems, knowledge applications, databases, processes and other infrastructure
7. report on knowledge embedded in business network, which includes connections outside the organization
8. Percentage of total workforce represented in formal joint management committees that help monitor and advise on employees-customers-supplier relations
9. Workers who are involved in occupational activities who have a high incidence or high risk, talent and know-how of employees needed to achieve goals

In recent years, the importance of risk management has been evidenced in the corporate sector. Risk management is important because effective risk management improves the company's performance by contributing to reduce fraud, managing potential threats, and more efficient use of resources. Taking and managing risk is the very essence of business survival and growth (Axelos Global Best Practise, 2014).

Corporate Governance Disclosure

Corporate governance balances shareholder, director, and management accountability (Apochi & Agbi, 2022). Accountability demands transparency and effective correction of mistakes (Dasaraju & Subramanyam, 2014). Its governance principles assist stakeholders monitor controls, resolve conflicts of interest, and ensure transparency (Buallay, Hamdan, & Zureigat 2017). Good corporate governance follows rules, regulations, and laws, especially those connected to economic, environmental, and social issues, and takes corrective action to ensure the firm's long-term existence (Buallay, 2020). This includes the board of directors' interactions with shareholders, management, auditors, regulatory organisations, and other company players (Okolie & Igaga 2021). Corporate governance defines decision-making and stakeholder rights and duties. Thus, corporate governance controls the company internally to satisfy stakeholders.

Corporate governance is the way an organization is directed, administrated and controlled. According to Blair (2015), corporate governance refers to the whole set of cultural, legal and institutional arrangements that determine what organizations could do, who controls them, how that control is exercised, and how the risks and return from the activities they undertake are allocated. In addition, the corporate governance structure specifies the distribution of rights and responsibilities among different participants in the organization, such as the board, managers, shareholders and other stakeholders, and spells out the regulations and procedures for making decisions on corporate affairs. Corporate governance covers a wide range of arrangements and aspects and scholars classify them into internal and external mechanisms.

Firms Performance

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. This term is used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time, and can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation (Okeke, 2015).

There are many different ways to measure financial performance, but all measures should be taken in aggregation. Line items such as revenue from operations, operating income or cash flow from operations can be used, as well as total unit sales. Furthermore, the analyst or investor may wish to look deeper into financial statements and seek out margin growth rates or any declining debt. Return on Equity, Return on Assets and Net Assets Per Share were used as a performance measurement in the prior expectations of Nahiba (2017), Brockman (2015), Oliveira, Rodrigues and Craig, (2015), Raheman, Salleh, Afza and Chek (2014), Abd.Hamid, Abdul Aziz, Dora and Said (2017) and Rouf (2016) etc

For the purpose of this study, one accounting based measurement (ROE) was used. i.e Return on Equity (ROE) was used to measure financial performance as used by Oliveira, Rodrigues and Craig, (2015), Raheman, Salleh, Afza and Chek (2014). This was captured as Net Profit After Tax divided by Total Equity i.e (ROE) This is expressed mathematically as

$$ROE = \frac{NPAT}{\text{Total Equity}}$$

Total Equity

The market valuation of a company shows shareholders its potential. Managers are expected to improve the company's market value to maximize investor returns. A rise in a company's share price indicates increased wealth (Ugwu & Nwakoby, 2020). Conversely, poor growth prospects lower corporate value. Thus, a good performance measure shows growth (Gikonyo, 2008). Performance is hard to define and quantify. Scholars have three alternatives for measuring business success. For instance, accounting, market, or both-based measurements. Many researchers prefer accounting-based performance ratios like ROA and ROE. Tobin's Q and other market-based indicators have been used by other experts. Accounting-based measures predict sustainability performance better (McGuire, Sundgren, & Schneeweis 1988) and are easier to manipulate (López, Garcia, & Rodriguez 2007) since they represent firm behaviour. However, market-based metrics assume shareholders are the dominant stakeholder group (Orlitzky, Schmidt, & Rynes 2003) and have an information imbalance between managers and shareholders (Cordeiro & Sarkis, 1997). Due to critiques of accounting-based measures, numerous research (Callan & Thomas, 2009) use a mix of market- and accounting-based variables. This study used accounting- and market-based metrics.

Theoretical Framework

The Legitimacy Theory

This study employs legitimacy theory as a theoretical framework. This theory was propounded by Donovan in the year 1984. The legitimacy theory presents two basic ideas whereby corporate organizations need to legitimize their activities and this legitimacy process provides benefits to the organization. Disclosing quality Non Financial Information is a way for companies to legitimize their activities. The benefit from the legitimacy process is represented by firm's profitability. Legitimacy theory presumed that a corporation will act to ensure that its activities

and actions were congruent with whom it believed has the necessary attributes to affect the corporation's image and ultimately, existence (Donavan, 1984).

Suchman (1995) described legitimacy theory as a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs and definitions. Using the legitimacy perspective, firms voluntarily disclose non financial information to show that they are conforming to the expectations and values of the society within which they operate. According to Guthrie and Parker (2009), they argue that if the legitimacy explanation holds true, the corporate disclosure policies will react to major social and environmental events.

Empirical Review

Precious, Eno and Joseph, (2025) examined the effect of non-mandatory information disclosures on market value added of consumer goods companies listed on Nigerian Exchange Group from 2014-2023. The research design adopted for the study was ex post facto, secondary data were employed and purposive sampling technique was adopted to select 16 out of 21 listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The method of data analysis employed for the study was ordinary least square regression analysis and the statistical package employed was E-views version 10. The results obtained from the regression analysis revealed that corporate governance disclosure does not have a significant effect on market value added; environmental performance disclosure has a significant negative effect on market value added while social donations and gifting disclosure does not have any significant effect on market value added of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. It was thus concluded that non mandatory information disclosures have a significant effect on shareholders' wealth maximization of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria. Based on this, it was recommended that management of listed consumer goods firms should highlight key governance practices, board effectiveness and disclose these practices to signal the investors of their responsible activities

Soomiyol, Adesoji and Yua, (2025) examined environmental, social and governance disclosure and performance of listed industrial goods companies in Nigerian from 2019 –2023. The independent variable was the ESG disclosure while the dependent variable was the market value. From 2019-2023, 13 industrial goods companies were examined out of the population of 14. Data were collected from the annual reports of the sampled companies and analyzed using panel random effect multiple regression model. It was found that environmental, social and governance disclosure all have positive and significant effect on market value of the companies examined. It was concluded that changes in the market value of the companies is as a result of the changes in the ESG disclosure of the companies. It was generally recommended that industrial goods companies should continue to review and adapt ESG disclosure policies that will continue to improve the market value of the companies through the attraction of more investors.

Atube and Okolie, (2024) explored the impact of non-financial information disclosures on the performance of non-financial services firms listed in Nigeria. It utilized an ex-post facto research design on panel data extracted from annual financial reports of selected firms spanning from 2013 to 2022. The methodology involved Generalized Linear Models (GLS) regression analysis, performed using E-Views V.9.0 software. Diagnostic tests were conducted to ensure compliance with panel assumptions, and hypotheses were evaluated based on the specific model formulated. The study utilized two models with dependent variables being accounting-based (Return on Equity - ROE) and market-based (Net Assets per Share - NAPS) to measure various independent variables (environmental, social, corporate governance, and forward looking disclosures). With p-values of 0.000 and 0.0433 for the models ROE and NAPS, respectively, the analysis's findings showed that environmental disclosures significantly and favourably affect the performance of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria. Social disclosures had negative p-values in both NAPS and ROE (0.0113 and 0.1310, respectively). However, corporate governance was statistically significant in ROE but negligible in NAPS. Additionally, with p-values of 0.0000 and 0.0230 for ROE and NAPS, respectively, the study demonstrated that forward-looking information positively and significantly impacted the performance of quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that

non-financial information disclosure has a mixed effect on the financial performance of quoted firms in Nigeria's non-financial services sector. It recommends regulatory standardization for forward-looking disclosures. Furthermore, investors are advised to consider future investment projections alongside financial statements to gain a comprehensive understanding of a firm's future outlook.

Muyiwa, Gbenga, Joseph and Olayinka, (2024) in the dynamic landscape of corporate reporting and stakeholder engagement, the significance of non-financial disclosure has gained considerable prominence. As businesses strive for sustainable growth and investors increasingly recognize the value of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors, understanding the nexus between non-financial disclosure and firm performance becomes pivotal. This study endeavors to explore this relationship within the context of listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study encompassed a population of 21 listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The sample size was 21 firms, determined through census sampling techniques. The research spanned from 2013 to 2022. FGLS regression model was used to examine the relationship between the variables studied. The results found that environmental disclosure and social disclosure had a positive and significant effect on the firm's performance. While governance disclosure had a negative and significant effect on the firm's performance. This implies that firms that engage in robust non-financial disclosure practices tend to experience better overall performance. The study concludes that non-financial disclosure, encompassing environmental, social, and governance aspects, plays a pivotal role in influencing the performance of listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Firms are encouraged to enhance their ESG reporting frameworks, aligning with stakeholder expectations and global sustainability trends.

Firmansyah, Umar, and Jibril (2023) examined how ESG disclosures affect Saudi Arabian listed corporations' performance. The study uses Bloomberg unbalanced panel data (2010–2020). ESG has greatly reduced TOBINSQ but has no effect on ROE. Environmental disclosure, an ESG component, favourably correlates with ROE but insignificantly negatively correlates with TOBINSQ. While social transparency negatively and insignificantly affects ROE, it lowers TOBINSQ. Governance disclosure dramatically reduced ROE and increased TOBINSQ. The findings also help regulators and legislators create rulebooks that ensure ESG efforts maximise shareholder profit. Baroma (2022) examined the prevalence of performance-related factors in Egyptian Stock Exchange-listed businesses' annual reports and voluntary disclosure. Multiple linear regression research looked at 49 Egyptian Stock Exchange-listed non-financial companies from 2017, 2018, and 2019. In 2018 and 2019, forward-looking disclosure improved profitability (EPS) and liquidity ratio. The 2017 forward-looking disclosure made them insignificant.

Shaikh (2022) used both descriptive and inductive analysis to look at how environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices and corporate performance relate in India. The results demonstrate that there are notable differences between GRI companies' market values (Tobin Q) and accounting performance (ROA and ROE). The social dimension negatively contributes, the environmental dimension seems daunting, and governance has a favorable impact on operational efficiency.

Okolie and Igaga (2021) assessed ESG disclosures and bank performance in Nigeria and South Africa. Census sample and content analysis covered 2012-2018. This data study employed descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, pooled regression, and independent t-tests. Nigeria and South Africa had high ESG disclosure increases. In addition, ESG reporting improves performance in Nigerian banks but hurts South African banks.

In a 2021 study of Shanghai and Shenzhen A-share listed businesses with ESG rating data from 2015 to 2019, Lei and Heng discovered that corporate ESG initiatives negatively affected firm performance. Non-state-owned and non-environmentally sensitive firms produced more evidence to support the aforesaid results, according to further research.

Forward-looking disclosures in Polish corporations' integrated reporting from 2016–2019 were evaluated by Bek-Gaik and Surowiec (2021). In 73 integrated reports, qualitative narratives about strategy, growth possibilities, and industry or market risk received more attention than investment projects, plans for

product research and development, financial risk, and industry or market risk. The study also showed that integrated reporting's forward-looking information and the company's financial performance are linked.

Corporate non-financial transparency and business performance were examined by Ugwu and Nwakoby (2020). 2015 data from 10 listed industrial products manufacturers was used. Three independent non-financial disclosure factors were ICD, RMD, and CGD. The data was analysed using multiple regression, the Multi-co linearity (VIF) test, and descriptive statistics. The study found that non-financial disclosures boost corporate performance.

In 2011-2018, Omaliko, Nwadiakor, and Nweze (2020) examined how social and environmental disclosures affected non-financial enterprises listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX Corporate social responsibility, environmental transparency, and business success (via net assets per share) are the study's major variables. Disclosures of corporate social and environmental practices affect firm performance by 5%.

Cloudy and Oday (2022) evaluated the impact of voluntary non-financial disclosure on listed companies. The study examined 50 Swedish companies with mandatory disclosure and 76 international companies with voluntary disclosure over seven years. Findings indicated a negative but insignificant impact on profitability for energy management and corporate social responsibility, while board diversity exhibited a positive but insignificant impact. The significant variable influencing profitability was the firm's size. The conclusion drawn was that disclosures related to energy management, corporate social responsibility, and board diversity had no significant impact on the financial performance of manufacturing companies, irrespective of engaging in mandatory or voluntary non-financial disclosure. These findings negate the findings of Abdulateif (2023) and Wang (2022).

Stefano and Clodia (2022) conducted a study exploring the impact of non-financial disclosure structure on reducing information asymmetry. Adopting a stakeholder perspective, the research analyzed non-financial disclosure structure in terms of depth, breadth, and concentration. Content analysis techniques were applied to reports released by U.S. firms listed in the S&P500 index from 2010 to 2020. The study utilized content and Bid-Ask spread data to test hypotheses. Findings showed that both the level and range of stakeholder-related subjects covered in reports contributed to diminishing information asymmetry. Companies consistently distributing information across various stakeholder categories experienced reduced opacity and information asymmetry. These findings were in line with the findings of Abdulateif (2023) and Wang (2022) but contradicted the findings of Cloudy Oday (2022).

Odugbemi and Igbekoyi (2021) re-examined economic performance indices, focusing on environmental reporting for Nigerian-listed oil and gas firms. The study explored the impact of environmental practice disclosures on economic performance, encompassing 11 oil and gas organizations from 2011 to 2020. Results revealed that certain environmental practices, such as pollution control policy and research and development, had a significant positive effect on earnings per share (EPS). However, aspects like compliance with environmental laws showed insignificant or negative effects on EPS.

Igbekoyi et al. (2021) investigated environmental accounting disclosure and its impact on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria. The study evaluated compliance and the effect of environmental disclosure on financial performance, focusing on multinational companies from 2011 to 2020. Findings indicated the oil and gas sector exhibited the lowest compliance. Additionally, environmental accounting disclosure had a significant positive impact on earnings per share (EPS) but a negative and insignificant effect on return on assets (ROA).

Dilling (2020) globally explored sustainability reporting, examining distinctions in size, financial performance, capital structure, and corporate governance between companies publishing G3 sustainability reports and those that do not. Findings revealed that European firms in the energy or production sector with higher profit margins tend to produce high-quality sustainability reports, while corporations with higher long-term growth rates are less inclined. The study emphasizes the importance of globally recognized sustainability reporting standards.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted the *Ex post facto* and longitudinal research design because secondary data that was sourced from financial publications such as the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) Fact Book and Daily Official List for the study. To analyze the data, the study used statistical tools involving the Descriptive Statistics, correlation analysis and the Ordinary Least Square Regressions (OLS).

Model Specifications

The equations and variables used for the study given below are adaptation and modifications from the work of Safdar, Hazoor, Toheed and Ammara (2013) studied the effect of financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms. This study then tested this model in Nigeria.

The model is stated thus:

$$FV = f(ICD, ARMD)$$

Where,

FV = Firm Value

ICD = Intellectual Capital Disclosure

RMD = Risk Management Disclosure

The model was adopted and modified by the inclusion of corporate governance disclosure

$$FV = f(ICD, RMD, CGD)$$

The Econometric Equation Form of the Model is:

$$FV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ICD + \beta_2 RMD + \beta_3 CGD + \mu - - - - -1$$

Where,

$$FV = f(ICD, ARMD, CGD)$$

Where,

FV = Firm Value

ICD = Intellectual Capital Disclosure

RMD = Risk Management Disclosure

CGD = Corporate Governance Disclosure

β_0 and μ are the constant and error term respectively while β_1 and β_3 are the coefficient of financial disclosure.

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics result shows the mean (average) for each of the variables, their maximum values, minimum values, standard deviation and the Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics (normality test). Table 4.1 below, provides the summary of the descriptive statistics of the selected firms.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	FV	ICD	RMD	CGD
Mean	0.586085	0.333737	0.463986	32.61932
Median	0.610000	0.360000	0.440000	32.06000
Maximum	1.190000	1.200000	0.760000	58.83000
Minimum	0.400000	0.010000	0.230000	19.01000
Std. Dev.	0.279916	0.195375	0.104344	8.801715
Skewness	0.673540	0.936864	1.037788	0.749291
Kurtosis	3.476098	5.109342	4.069279	3.195801
Jarque-Bera	23.90015	93.20049	63.82646	26.74281
Probability	0.000006	0.000000	0.000000	0.000002
Sum	164.6900	93.78000	130.3800	9166.030
Sum Sq. Dev.	21.93889	10.68798	3.048536	21691.65
Observations	30	30	30	30

Source: Descriptive Statistics Result Using e-view 8

The descriptive statistics result shows a mean value of 0.59 for firm value. The mean value shows that measuring performance using firm value. The result shows that on the average the selected firms used in the study has positive performance on the average within the period under study. The difference between the mean, maximum and minimum shows that some of company's incurred losses within the period.

Intellectual Capital Disclosure which shows a mean value of 0.33, maximum value of 1.20 and minimum value of 0.01. This shows that only some of the management is effective in the utilization of the firm's resources effective.

The result shows that the average of risk management disclosure is 0.463986, maximum value of 0.760000 and minimum value of 0.230000.

The Jarque Bera and its probability which test the level of normality of the data shows that firm value, intellectual capital disclosure, risk management disclosure and corporate governance disclosure are normally distributed at one percent significant level.

Correlation analysis

In examining the relationship among the variables, the study employed the Pearson correlation analysis; the results are presented in table 4.2

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

	<i>FV</i>	<i>ICD</i>	<i>RMD</i>	<i>CGD</i>
<i>FV</i>	1.000000	0.211078	0.282136	0.097123
<i>ICD</i>	0.211078	1.000000	0.097123	0.282136
<i>RMD</i>	0.282136	0.145651	1.000000	0.211078
<i>CGD</i>	0.097123	0.100016	0.310316	1.000000

Source: E-view 8

The findings from the correlation analysis table, shows that firm value have a positive relationship with intellectual capital disclosure, risk management disclosure, corporate governance disclosure. The positive relationship between firm value and intellectual capital disclosure, risk management disclosure, corporate governance disclosure indicates that the more the intellectual capital disclosure the higher the firm value. Again an increase in the level of intellectual capital disclosure will improve the firm value. the result of the correlation analysis indicate the existence of positive relationship between firm value and corporate governance disclosure, the implication is that an increase in the level of corporate governance disclosure will enhance the firm value of the selected companies

In checking for multi-co linearity the study noticed that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This indicates the absence of multi-co linearity problem in the model used for the analysis and also justifies the use of the ordinary least square.

The Ordinary Least Square Regression

In this section, we provide the benchmark test of the significance of the independent variables in explaining the effect non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: FV

Method: Least Squares

Date: 11/09/25 Time: 15:27

Sample: 2018 2023

Included observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.667553	0.824890	10.809263	0.0260

ICD	0.164745	1.010577	2.163021	0.0058
RMD	-0.518247	0.672745	1.770347	0.2183
CGD	0.068816	0.039042	2.762604	0.0302
<hr/>				
R-squared	0.712561	Mean dependent var		4.676947
Adjusted R-squared	0.655073	S.D. dependent var		7.153306
S.E. of regression	6.953540	Akaike info criterion		6.888364
Sum squared resid	1208.793	Schwarz criterion		7.165910
Log likelihood	-100.7696	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.978837
F-statistic	19.349696	Durbin-Watson stat		2.971283
Prob(F-statistic)	0.006525			

Source: Eviews 9.0

The results from coefficient (0.667553) and the probability value ($p = 0.0260 < 0.05$) showed that firm value (FV) which is the dependent variable (Y) is positive: This means that if all the independent, (explanatory) variables (X) are held constant, firm value as a dependent variable (Y) will grow by (0.667553) units in annual-wide basis.

Intellectual Capital Disclosure: The results from coefficient (0.164745) and the probability value ($p = 0.0058 < 0.05$) showed that intellectual capital disclosure had positive and significant effect on firm value. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis: intellectual capital disclosure has positive and significant effect on firm value in Nigeria, is accepted

Risk Management Disclosure: The results from coefficient (0.518247) and the probability value ($p = 0.0183 < 0.05$) showed that risk management disclosure has positive and significant effect on r firm value. This means that the alternate hypothesis two: risk management disclosure has positive and significant effect on firm value in Nigeria, is accepted.

Corporate Governance Disclosure: The results from coefficient (0.068816) and the probability value ($P = 0.0302 < 0.05$) showed that corporate governance disclosure has positive and significant effect on firm value. This means that the alternate hypothesis three: corporate governance disclosure has no positive and significant effects firm value in Nigeria, is accepted.

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.712561$) showed that about 71% of changes in the on the firm value in Nigeria is accounted for by the level of non financial disclosure. This implies that non financial disclosure ntrol variables is one major contributor on firm value in Nigeria

The F-statistics (19.349696; $p < 0.05$) indicated that all the variables of the model (non financial disclosure variables) have significant effect on firm value in Nigeria. The Durbin Watson statistics (2.971283) showed that there was no autocorrelation in the model employed.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The regression result indicates that intellectual capital disclosure, risk management disclosure and corporate governance disclosure has positive and significant effects firm value in Nigeria. The study thus concludes that non financial disclosure on firm value of listed firms in Nigeria.

The study recommend that management of quoted firms in Nigeria should formulate policy that will be geared toward enhancing intellectual capital disclosure that management of quoted firms in their drive to

enhance firm value; management should increase and improve risk management disclosure and that management of quoted firm should improve in corporate governance disclosure

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